

Capability-Maturity & Community Engagement - Design Statement

A FAIRsFAIR Discussion Paper v01.00

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In brief

This paper proposes a design approach to evaluating capability in particular areas of focus within an entity, and the level of adoption, practice and collaboration displayed related to policy, and standardisation.

Capability-Maturity

- Define the entity being assessed for capability and maturity. Organisation, part of an organisation, component service etc.
- Define the areas of focus within the entity that are being addressed.
- Take a consistent approach to evaluating areas of focus as: initial (1), managed (2) and defined (3).
- Align with CMMI 2.0¹ definitions to permit expansion to more in-depth approaches: quantitatively managed (4) and optimizing (5).
- Acknowledge the risks of assigning high overall 'maturity' to an entity when some areas of focus display low capability.

Community engagement: practice awareness, adoption and collaboration

Address these codependent concepts with their own tiers to allow independent evaluation.

- Assign ascending values of awareness, adoption and collaboration, to the areas of focus.
- Evaluate how extensively the entity being assessed is raising awareness of community practice, supporting its adoption, or actively collaborating to develop it further :
 - within the entity being assessed,
 - and/or in networks joining the entity to its wider ecosystem

These two scales are logically separate, though a model design could specify that a particular level of community engagement is necessary to demonstrate a particular tier of capability/maturity.

¹ <https://cmmiinstitute.com/learning/appraisals/levels>

Introduction

Understanding our levels of capability in particular areas and how these contribute to overall maturity allows us to understand our current status and to identify and invest in areas where we want to improve and monitor our progress. This applies to both self-assessment and external evaluation. The approach can be adjusted to address a range of entities including organisations, parts of organisations and component services. It should be possible to apply these approaches to repositories and other organisations providing data infrastructure (RDI) and also to organisations providing funding (RFO) or performing research (RPO).

In addition to existing capability and maturity models there are several under development or review within the EOSC² and trustworthy digital repository (TDR) space.³ The model designers need the freedom to develop and evolve independently, but recognize the risk to implementers of having a confusing range of non-interoperable and resource-intensive systems to choose from. This text reflects the evolving design statement being developed within the FAIRsFAIR⁴ project.

Modelling Considerations

A methodology like CMMI 2.0⁵ aims to address a whole organisation by assessing capability across all practice areas and evaluating overall maturity. Within FAIRsFAIR and related efforts the scope may be narrower than a whole organisation e.g. long-term preservation (where a repository may sit within a wider organisation) or research data management (excluding some aspects of organisational infrastructure). In all cases it is important to define the scope of the 'entity' (organisation, service etc.) being assessed. Within these entities, the model designer may have different *areas of focus* that are analogous to the practice areas of CMMI.

Our project approach is to concentrate on three tiers of capability: initial (1), managed (2) and defined (3), using definitions (see below) that remain aligned with those of CMMI 2.0. We consider that this provides the minimum necessary level of granularity in self-assessment, peer-review, and evaluation to enable progress planning and monitoring. An initial three-tier approach avoids overburdening an organisation applying a capability/maturity approach for the first time. Maintaining alignment with CMMI provides a common reference point between models and provides a methodology for addressing higher levels of complexity and overall maturity if required.

Some models include a null response ('level 0' or 'incomplete' or 'we have not considered this'). These are excluded for simplicity, though they are implied by this three tier model. This model is compatible with scenarios where *capability* scores are combined to calculate overall *maturity* as 'quantitatively managed' (4) and 'optimizing' (5). Tiers 4 and 5 may be necessary for organisational interoperability e.g. between those providing the 'backbone' of the EOSC. However, tiers 4/5 should be seen as high bars and potentially resource-intensive. Model designers and those that use the models for assessments should be persuaded to avoid inflating evaluations to satisfy an impractical desire to score highly.

² <https://eosc.eu/>

³ For further detail, see Capability-Maturity Modeling and Landscape, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4005598>

⁴ <https://www.fairsfair.eu/>

⁵ <https://cmmiinstitute.com/learning/appraisals/levels>

Applying this design approach makes things simpler and more comparable for those using the three tiers, but it also allows extensions for those that need it. By aligning where we can, we avoid having a large number of approaches that seem similar but are actually hard to implement together.

The outcome is that models with different perspectives (policy frameworks, trustworthiness, FAIRness etc.) but comparable ‘scoring’ mechanisms may be applied to the same entity e.g. research data support service, repository, data service.

Models should avoid mixed criteria within the same tiers. For example, the relevance of a metric should be handled with a separate statement of applicability and not as part of the capability/maturity tiers.

Tiers should also focus on a ‘snapshot’ of current levels. The fact that an organisation is currently working to move from one tier to another (“in progress”, “partial”, “in the implementation phase”) should be addressed outside the tiers

“Planning to” and “development ongoing” can be applied to movements between tiers over time. Tiers 1 and 2 can be reached without coordinated practice across the entity (CMMI equates this to a ‘project’ perspective in contrast to an ‘organisation’). But progress from initial (2) to managed (3) always implies coordination of practice across different areas of focus: shared policies, procedures, standards etc. Progress is measured by comparing snapshots over time.

These design criteria permit the design and implementation of a range of capability and maturity models that simplify implementation even when applied together.

In this compatible but simplified FAIRsFAIR approach (based on the CMMI levels below) each tier description is applied to areas of focus in entity (organisation, repository, service) being evaluated:

1. **Initial.** *May be incomplete and falling short of the intent of the area of focus. Aware of and addressing performance issues.*
2. **Managed.** *Limited but complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus. Although lacking full alignment with overall organisational standards and practice, identifies and monitors performance objectives. Includes and builds on level 1.*
3. **Defined.** *Complete coverage that delivers the full intent of the area of focus and aligns with overall organisational standards and practice. Identifies and monitors performance objectives that expand alignment to the whole organisation.*

Diagram: Comparison of focus areas vs entity-wide tiers

For levels 3 and above care should be taken when moving from evaluating capability in an area of focus to assessing maturity across the organisation. If an entity has high capability in most areas of focus, but very low capability for one significant area (e.g. information security), evaluation outcomes should not assign a misleading level of overall maturity.

Diagram: FAIRsFAIR Capability and Maturity Perspective

Some modelling approaches seek to assess the degree to which an entity communicates about and engages with policy and community practice. There may be cases where this is an explicit condition of meeting a particular capability/maturity level, but in general such assessments are on a separate scale. Our draft approach considers an entity in terms of practice awareness, adoption and community collaboration:

Awareness: *monitors community practice and makes local practitioners aware of it.*

Adoption: *also supports practitioners to embed community practice locally.*

Collaboration: *also engages with the design, development and review of community practice. Consults and collaborates widely, potentially taking a community coordination and leadership role. Driving maintenance and updates of existing practice and identifying new areas for the development of policy and implementation standards. Actively communicating and promoting existing and emerging approaches to the immediately impacted communities and the wider data infrastructure landscape.*

The level of adoption possible and the appropriate standards and policies may depend whether the organisation is funding (RFO), performing research (RPO) or providing data infrastructure (RDI).

Appendix: Capability Levels from CMMI 2.0⁶

Diagram: CMMI Levels Overview

Level 1 initial Incomplete approach to meeting the intent of the Practice Area. May or may not be meeting the intent of any practice. Addresses performance issues.

Level 2: Managed. Subsumes level 1 practices. Simple, but complete set of practices that address the full intent of the Practice Area. Does not require the use of the organizational assets. Identifies and monitors progress towards project performance objectives.

Level 3: Defined. Builds on level 2 practices. Uses organizational standards and tailoring to address project and work characteristics. Projects use and contribute to organization assets. Focuses on achieving both project and organizational performance objectives.”

Level 4: Quantitatively Managed. Measured and controlled. Organization is data-driven with quantitative performance improvement objectives that are predictable and align to meet the needs of internal and external stakeholders.

Level 5: Optimizing. Stable and flexible. Organization is focused on continuous improvement and is built to pivot and respond to opportunity and change. The organization’s stability provides a platform for agility and innovation.

⁶ <https://cmminstitute.com/learning/appraisals/levels>

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